

THE ROLE OF IMAGE IN LEADERSHIP

Samiyev Baxtiyor Norboboyevich

Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture 2nd year student

Abstract: *Creating an image is a complex and long-term task. A successful image - image appears from the step-by-step conduct of behavior and actions towards a goal. This article discusses the role of image in the management processes of modern leaders. In addition, the features of the leader's image were also mentioned.*

Key words: *Modern management style, image in work style, leadership, state and society, national tradition.*

Since the years of independence, a lot of attention has been paid to connecting every holy thing with a human name, human factor, human intelligence. The image of the state is related to peaceful and happy living of people.

Image is an English word that means “image”, “image” and “image”. This is an image formed in the minds of people in relation to a specific person, organization or social object. It stores a large amount of emotionally decorated information about the perceived object and motivates certain social behavior. The image provides information about its owner, changes quickly, affects the mind, emotions, activities and behavior of people. Image is the only factor that affects people’s psyche and appearance. A properly chosen image will increase a person’s self-confidence. People can attract the attention of others, establish friendly relations, and show

courtesy through their image.

Creating the image of a modern leader is his face, clothes, heart, sound mind, behavior culture, a person who perfectly masters the art of management, human qualities such as competence, knowledge, thinking, professional skills, prudence, modesty, politeness, it is to show the influence of a person, to increase his reputation, to be respected, relying on the traditions of beauty, morality, teaching and example, teacher and student. Image helps bring out the best in today's leaders. It hides the personal negative characteristics of the modern leader. For example, people can be distracted by existing defects in the leader's makeup, dress decorations, style, hairstyle, and work performance. An attractive image attracts people's attention involuntarily and leaves a good impression on others.

This is called the image approach of the leader's work style. The main tasks of the image are:

- ❖ Education of modern man;
- ❖ improving professional skills of specialists in various fields;
- ❖ distinguish types of professional activities such as PR specialist, stylist, image maker;
- ❖ helping to overcome the physical shyness characteristic of people and to reveal their rich spiritual world;

❖ tasks such as identifying positive qualities hidden in a person and helping to realize them. These tasks contribute to the development of the main image of leaders, but also of each person.

The leader's work style is his unique approach to solving one or another issue in the management process. When a leader makes a decision, organizes its implementation, and supervises the work of subordinates, he performs his duties in accordance with his duties. However, each leader acts in his own way, in the management process, in ways that are suitable for him and determine his leadership style. Just as no two people are exactly the same, no leadership style is exactly the same [1:104]. The style of leadership is formed in the relationship of leaders with their subordinates, in their mutual relations. The leader's work style is determined by the individual potential, qualities, and individual characteristics of the management body.

The spiritual qualities of a leader are understood as all the positive signs that are expressed in his language, expressed in his language, and in all his actions. The spiritual qualities of a leader are talent, research, modern knowledge, patriotism, faith, piety, justice, kindness, faith, purity, honesty, loyalty [2; 58].

The formation of the leader's image is manifested in interpersonal relations, in drawing the correct conclusions from difficult situations, in the ability to use anger and kindness instead. At all times, the principle of respect and attention at work inspired employees and was clearly visible as a result of this work. The friendly relations of the leader in many cases led to the elimination of conflicts, the prevention of cases of partiality and indifference.

In this regard, in turn, managers, that is, leaders, help image makers to have

fewer negative vices and more work-related qualities. Only intellectuals who believe in themselves and their will deserve the respect and admiration of others, therefore, the attention and respect of employees allows to replenish and restore bioenergetic power. The national faith and spiritual image of the leader, his leadership behavior also indicate the positive image of the leader. Here I can remember one sentence. That is, as the famous writer Jonathan Swift said: “Not many people are good-looking in society, but most people can be likable”. I wouldn’t be wrong if I say that this idea is a proof of what I said above.

In addition to these qualities that make up the spirituality of a leader, there are also human vices. They are an obstacle to the formation of the leader’s spirituality. For example, Professor E. Goziev lists the following fifteen such vices:

- ✦ Lack of self-control;
- ✦ Disruption of personal values;
- ✦ Ambiguity of personal goal;
- ✦ Derailment of self-improvement;
- ✦ Lack of problem-solving skills;
- ✦ The presence of defects in the creative approach;
- ✦ Inability to influence people;
- ✦ Inadequate understanding of management activity features;
- ✦ Weak leadership skills;
- ✦ Lack of ability to teach others, to give them lessons, to teach them;
- ✦ Low ability to integrate the labor team;
- ✦ Inability to attract the attention of others with news;

- ✚ Lack of culture of dealing with people;
- ✚ Laziness in intelligence and insight;
- ✚ Weakness of business ability [2;58].

For a leader, these aspects are dominant in forming his image: firstly, calmness, secondly, not showing emotion, thirdly, business mood, and fourthly, being cold. Calmness – effectively listens to the problem of the employee who has entered the reception, “infects” the mood of work to other teammates, does not express emotion, does not bring the attitude of others to one’s problem, and being cold leads to fairness in solving the problem. That is why the mood from the morning’s work remains after the end of the working day [3:14].

It is clear that through this we can learn about the leader’s work style, image, and spiritual and cultural potential. The leader requires not only image but also national culture in his work style. A leader who wants to be cultured and successful should observe the following: fulfill the given promise on time, keep his word under any circumstances, be indifferent and objective to useless suggestions that cause wasted time, politely and politely reject proposals that are not useful to him and his team, be confident in any circle or event, avoid big departures, as a leader, do not disappoint subordinates to educate people, to encourage their productive work and initiative, not to be selfish, not to forget that one's own opinion is not always right, that there are other opinions and points of view that are not completely bad, failure in their work, interruptions and mistakes qualities such as careful analysis, controlling anger among employees and at work, not losing patience [4:44].

In conclusion, some leaders or ordinary people may not be beautiful, but if they have a lot of spiritual qualities, they attract the attention of others. A person who has

the ability to feel the inner world of a person, to understand it, to feel the solution of future negotiations, or to change the subject by knowing the mood of his interlocutor, will only lead to the realization of a good goal and prevent evil. . But the image of a modern leader today is a reflection of his worldview and spirituality. Spirituality is the cultural criterion of all leaders and people. A spiritually mature person distinguishes between what is good and what is bad and makes rational decisions in life. Determination of spiritual and moral qualities is an integral part of the image of modern leaders. After all, a competent, intellectual leader with spiritual potential is the backbone of the country and the supporter of the future generation.

References:

1. A.Haydarov. Ijodiy ishlab chiqarish faoliyatini rejalashtirish,tashkil etish va boshqarish. – T. “Yangi nashr” nashriyoti. 2016-yil, 104-bet.
2. Yusupov E. Inson kamolotining ma’naviy asoslari. T., Universitet, 2018, 58-b.
3. Ma’naviyat asoslari 10-11-sinf: O’rta ta’lim maktablarining 10-11-sinflari va o’rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta’limi muassasalari uchun darslik /V. Qo‘chqorov, O. Mahmudov, Z. Zamonov. – Birinchi nashr. – Tosh-kent.: “Yangiyo‘l poligraf servis”, 2017. – 62-67-betlar.
4. S.To‘ychiyeva. Madaniyat va san’at muassasalari faoliyatini tashkil etish va boshqarish. – T. “Fan va ta’lim” nashriyoti. 2020-yil, 114-bet.
5. Muhammadjonova L.A. Abidjanova F.A. Etiket. o‘quv qo‘llanma. –T., Universitet. 2022.
6. M.Sharifxo‘jayev, Y.Abdullayev.Menejment. – “O‘qituvchi” nashriyoti. 2001-yil, 44-bet.

7. Mo‘minmirzo Zokir o‘g‘li Xolmo‘minov. 2017-2022-yillar mobaynida madaniyat va san‘at sohasida amalga oshirilgan ishlar sarhisobi. “Oriental Art and Culture” jurnali. Qo‘qon 2022. <https://scholar.google.com>
8. Samiyev Baxtiyor Norbobo o‘g‘li, Ilmiy rahbar: Mo‘minmirzo Xolmo‘minov. Huquqiy madaniyatning shaxs va davlat bilan uzviy bog‘liqligi. “Conference on Universal Science Research 2023”. 2023/2/12. 240-242 b
9. Mo‘minmirzo Xolmo‘minov, Asilbek Qolqanatov. O‘zbekistonda madaniy-ma‘rifiy ishlar va kutubxonalar faoliyati (XX asr tajribalaridan). “Oriental Art and Culture” jurnali. Qo‘qon 2022. <https://scholar.google.com>
10. Mo‘minmirzo Xolmo‘minov, Asilbek Qolqanatov. Himmat – inson umrining bezagi. Kutubxona uz. Jurnali. 2022/4/56. O‘zbekiston Milliy kutubxonasi matbaa bo‘limi. 12-13-betlar.